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Downscaling climate impacts and decarbonisation pathways in EU Islands, and enhancing socioeconomic and non-market evaluation of Climate Change for Europe, for 2050 and beyond

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1 Abstract

The fate of the beaches in European islands is of paramount importance as it is one of the main assets for touristic activities. Sea level rise and changes in the wave climate would put a risk the beaches as a significant loss of beach area could be expected. Quantitative projections of beach evolution was not available for most European islands, mainly due to the difficulties associated to the required computations. In this work, a new methodology has been developed allowing cost-effective and yet accurate estimate of wave runup for different types of sand beaches. This, combined with recent projections of sea level rise and wave climate, has allowed a quantification of the flood level for all European islands as a function of time horizon GHG scenario and beach granulometry. In a second step, this information has been transferred to coast retreat and beach area loss for the Balearic islands, where detailed information on beach granulometry and current area was available.

Results for the coastline retreat show that, for the Balearic Islands, under mean conditions, will be 7m at mid-century and 11m at the end of the century, with significant differences across the region depending on the exposure to strong waves. The retreat under mean conditions is typically larger in the south/southwest area and obviously larger at the end of the century. Under extreme conditions, the retreat increases to 18m at mid-century and 22 m at the end of the century, but in this case the heterogeneity is larger, with some spots where the coastline shows almost a retreat similar to the mean conditions and others where it can double that value.

Related to the beach surface loss, at mid-century, it ranges from ~34% under scenario RCP2.6 to ~51% under scenario RCP8.5. At the end of the century the percentage increases to 45% and 70%, respectively. Under extreme conditions (i.e. temporary conditions), the percentages range between 72% and 79% at mid-century, and between 77% and 86% at the end of the century, depending on the scenario.

2 Introduction

The 20th century has witnessed an unprecedented population expansion and a revolution in the ways of life and work, which together have enhanced and renewed the uses of coastal areas. Following this context, the beaches generally constitute the most valued elements of the coast, (Galofré et al., 2001). That has generated a long list of actions and aggressions that strongly limits the capacity of beaches to adapt to environmental changes, making them specially vulnerable to impacts derived from climate change.

Beaches play a fundamental role in two main aspects. On the one hand, regarding to socioeconomic level, they represent a focus of interest for sun and beach tourism, having a great positive impact on the economy of the region. As a second main aspect, but no less important, is that beaches serve as a natural barrier to decrease the energy coming from the storm events associated with high winds, waves and over-rising sea levels, which can cause a huge amount of damages to coastal infrastructure. In that sense it is worth mentioning that storms constitute a significant hazard in coastal regions, triggering geomorphological change and threatening harbour facilities, coastal tourism infrastructure, houses, and even human lives, through storm-surge

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flooding and wave attack (Vousdoukas et al., 2012). In consequence, understanding the coastal response to environmental forcing is a relevant topic as it is the first step for an appropriate management of the coastal area in the long term (Agulles et al., 2019).

Among all the processes occurring at the scale of the beach, flooding becomes one of the most important, if not the most important one. Flooding, either permanent or during episodes, will reduce the usable area of the beach as well as their capacity as a natural barrier. The level of flooding is determined by the sea level and by the wave runup (set of discrete water level elevation maxima, measured on the foreshore, with respect to still water level, (Stockdon et al., 2006)). To address a realistic estimation of how waves and sea level variation can produce flood events, it would be necessary to have a historical record of waves and sea level near the beach, along with a detailed bathymetry. In addition, the beaches usually present different profiles depending on the period of the year. After the winter months, the profile is steep in the swash zone forming a barrier in the intertidal zone. During summer, it is common to find low energy levels associated with the incident waves, so the profile is modified until the barrier disappears, and a smooth slope is reached along the beach (Agulles et al., 2019). Therefore it would be recommended to have information, at least, about the summer and winter bathymetries.

Having a high resolution ($\sim 5\text{m}$) downscaling of waves and sea level near the coast along with a detailed bathymetry of all the beaches of all islands in the project, would be an unaffordable task. So, in order to address this issue, a new approach has been developed and validated against observations to obtain a cost-effective method to derive wave runup at beach scale. This has allowed to derive projections of beach reduction for all the sand beaches of the Balearic Islands under different greenhouse gases (GHG) emission scenarios. For the other islands, the lack of information on beach topography and beach cartography prevents to reach that degree of detail. Nevertheless, flood level has been projected for different beach profiles, so once the cartography of a particular beach is obtained, the surface reduction can be easily inferred.

3 Database

3.1 Sea level

Mean sea level rise has been modelled including all the factors that play a role. In particular at global scale, first, mass variations linked to the addition/removal of water from the ocean can be induced by land-based ice melting or by changes in the groundwater due to, basically, human activities. Second, thermal expansion due to ocean warming would also induce a rise of global mean sea level. Furthermore, regional changes are also expected and could induce a major contribution to total sea level rise at coastal scale. These are linked to the gravitational fingerprint of changes in the ocean mass, to changes in the circulation patterns (which in turn are related to the steric/density variations), to mass redistribution by atmospheric pressure and wind, and to land motion. All those factors cannot be modelled at the same time as they involve very different processes, so the typical approach is to use different models to cope with the different

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contributions. In this work we have followed the approach of Slangen et al., 2014 and Jordà and Gomis (2019), which is further described in the deliverable section on sea level rise.

3.2 Waves

Wave data has been obtained from two different ensembles of model simulations, one for the Mediterranean, where the complexity of the basin requires high resolution in the wave model and the wave forcing, and another one for the Atlantic islands. More details are provided in the deliverable section on wave extremes. For the Mediterranean, the ensemble of models developed by Lionello et al, (2016) is used. This ensemble consists on 6 simulations run with the WAM model at $1/4^\circ$ of spatial resolution and forced by the high resolution wind fields from the MedCORDEX ensemble which in turn is nested into CMIP5 global simulations. For the Atlantic islands the ensemble of global simulations produced by Hemer et al. (2013) has been selected. It has been created forcing the WaveWatch III model at 1° of spatial resolution with the outputs from 8 CMIP5 global simulations. The simulations are run for the period 1950-2100 thus covering the historical period as well as the whole 21st century under scenarios RCP8.5 and RCP4.5.

Finally, an important aspect is that no simulations for scenario RCP2.6 are available, so we have used a scaling approximation. Namely, the projected changes in sea level rise under RCP2.6 are considered to be about half of the projected changes under RCP4.5, while keeping the same spatial structure in each model. That is, the impact of the greenhouse gas concentration is basically a change in the intensity of a spatial pattern, which is model dependent. Therefore, in order to approximate the future evolution under the RCP2.6 scenario we have multiplied by 0.5 the changes modelled under RCP4.5.

3.3 Beach Topography

Information of the beaches of the Balearic Islands has been provided by the “Demarcación de Costas de les Illes Balears ” belonging to the “Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica (MITECO)”, government of Spain. The database consists of detailed information of 869 beaches located around the coast. In particular the database contains the coordinates of the beach contour, shape of the beach and a coarse estimate of the granulometry, along with other complementary information on services and uses.

4 Methods

To calculate the flood distance on a beach is necessary to take into account the contribution of the sea level rise and the energy of the incident waves. When the waves reach the coast, it breaks on the beach, producing a movement of ascent of the waterfront along the beach profile, commonly known in coastal engineering as Runup (Figure 1). The wave runup depends on the incoming wave conditions (significant wave height and peak period) and on the beach slope.

Figure 1. Sketch showing the contribution of waves and sea level to coastal flooding

As is not possible to have the value of the slope of all the beaches for all the islands, we have considered 11 equilibrium profiles corresponding to different granulometries of sand beaches. (for grain sizes ranging from 0.15 mm to 1 mm). The equilibrium profile is defined as the configuration to which the shape of the beach tends under a stationary situation of hydrodynamic conditions. This “ideal” concept of a equilibrium profile allows an approximate but faithful representation of the morphology of a beach, (Galofré et al., 2001). To do so, we use the Bernabeu formulation to design equilibrium profiles. That formulation considers two profile sections (the shoaling and break profile), see Figure 2. Under equilibrium conditions, it could be assumed that the energy of the wave in the breaking zone is saturated. It means that a wave propagating towards the coast varies its height due to the shoaling process, until reaching a critical value from which it becomes unstable and breaks, dissipating the excess of energy, (Bernabeu et al., 2001).

Figure 2. Bernabeu equilibrium profiles depending on several grain size (in mm, see legend). Land (black profiles), blue (breaking zone) and colors of the legend (shoaling zone).

The next step has been to calculate the wave runup for an ensemble of wave height/period pairs and for each one of the 11 beach profiles. The run up has been calculated using the Xbeach model. Xbeach is an open-source numerical model which originally was developed to simulate hydrodynamic and morphodynamic processes and impacts on sandy coasts with a domain size of kilometres and on the time scales of storms, (Roelvink et al., 2015). Xbeach model has been run to propagate 38 sea states, defined by typical wave height-period values that covers all the casuistic of waves around the regions of interest. Each sea state (pair of height-period values) has been simulated for 1 hour using the JONSWAP spectrum. Then, the runup has been diagnosed using the Ru2% parameter (the level only exceeded by 2% of the incident waves). As a result, we have obtained the Ru2% for each one of the 38 sea states and each beach profile (in total 38x11 = 418 cases). This has provided a transfer matrix for each beach profile (i.e. grain size) so we can reconstruct the wave runup time series from time series of wave height/period (Figure 3).

Once the wave data (height and period) has been extracted for each region, it has been classified depending on the direction of propagation (8 sectors). Also, for each island, the coast orientation has been computed in 10km transects, so for each portion of the coastline only the waves arriving perpendicular to the coast are considered for runup estimation. Then, using the transfer matrix each pair of wave height-period values perpendicular to the coast is transformed to runup. From those runup time series the 50th and 99th percentiles of the values are retained and added to the projected mean sea level rise and the 99th percentile of storm surge. This provides an estimate of the mean and extreme elevation at beach level. This has been repeated for the 11 types of beach profile (grain size), see Figure 3.

Figure 3. Runup results from Xbeach model for each grain size.

To clarify the steps followed, see the next figure (Figure 4),

Figure 4. Methodological scheme to obtain the Runup values as a function of significant wave height (H_s), period (T_p) and grain size

5 Results

The different components affecting to beach flooding have been compiled and described in deliverable 4.3. Here we present a summary with special emphasis in the Balearic Islands, where the beach data is available.

5.1 Mean Sea Level Rise

The results are presented in terms of averaged sea level rise for each region in Table 1 and the maps for the Balearic Islands in Figure 5. For consistency the maps for the other islands are included in the appendix of Deliverable 4.3. Nevertheless, the projected SLR is very uniform at regional scale and are not specially informative (see Figure 5). The results show slight differences among islands with relative differences in SLR lower than 25%. For instance, the largest SLR is found for Madeira under the RCP8.5 scenario at the end of the century (74.72 cm). For the same scenario and time frame the smallest SLR is found for the Baltic islands (56.60 cm), a 24% lower. Also, the SLR is expected to be larger in the Atlantic islands, and as expected also larger at the end of the century and under the RCP8.5 scenario.

Island	RCP2.6 2046-2065	RCP8.5 2046-2065	RCP2.6 2081-2100	RCP8.5 2081-2100
Balearic	12,46	32,93	24,92	65,86
Canary	13,64	37,03	27,29	74,06
Crete	11,60	31,74	23,19	63,48
Madeira	13,63	37,36	27,27	74,72
Sardinia	11,10	30,23	22,19	60,46
West	13,45	35,13	26,91	70,27
Azores	12,22	34,35	24,44	68,69
Baltic	9,91	28,30	19,82	56,60
Corsica	10,65	29,20	21,31	58,41
Cyprus	10,15	28,90	20,31	57,81
Malta	12,05	32,49	24,10	64,99
Sicily	11,48	31,25	22,96	62,50

Table 1. Projected sea level rise with respect to the present (1986-2005) values for the different islands and two time horizons, the near future (2046-2065) and the far future (2080-2100) under scenarios RCP2.6 and RCP8.5.

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Figure 5. Projected mean sea level rise (in cm) with respect to the present (1986-2005) mean sea level values for the Balearic Islands under scenario RCP2.6 (left) and RCP8.5 (right). The projected changes for the near future (2046-2065) are presented in the top row while the projected changes for the far future (2081-2100) are presented in the bottom row

5.2 Storm Surge

The results for storm surge are only available for the Mediterranean islands. They are presented in terms of maps including information about the present conditions and relative change (in %) with respect to those conditions. This has been decided for practical reasons as far as changes are difficult to be appreciated in the maps of absolute values. In particular, in the appendix of deliverable 4.3 there are the figures organized by islands and the example for the Balearic Islands is presented in Figure 6. The figure includes the 99th percentile of hourly sea level from the hindcast simulation for the period 1986-2005 (an average of them when more than one hindcast is available), and the relative change under RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 in two time horizons, 2046-2065 (near future) and 2081-2100 (far future). It is important to highlight that the model outputs have been interpolated to the island high resolution coastlines for visualization purposes. However, the original spatial resolution is way coarser.

As a summary of the results Table 2 shows showing the 99th percentile of sea level averaged in each region for the hindcast, and the two scenarios for the two periods. In all the regions a decrease in sea level is found being larger under scenario RCP8.5. In relative terms the averaged changes are lower than 15% even under the stronger scenario, in good agreement with the projections for wave storms (see below).

Region	Hindcast 1986-2005	RCP2.6 2046-2065	RCP85 2046-2065	RCP2.6 2081-2100	RCP85 2081-2100
Balearic	14,46	14,24	14,21	14,53	13,07
Crete	20,33	19,89	19,82	19,72	17,59
Sardinia	15,78	15,54	15,40	15,65	13,95
Corsica	17,45	17,21	17,14	17,33	15,90

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Cyprus	22,45	22,22	22,52	22,27	21,05
Malta	14,84	14,32	13,73	14,22	12,08
Sicily	15,46	15,03	14,47	14,96	12,73

Table 2. 99th percentile of atmospherically forced sea level (in cm) averaged in each region for the hindcast period, the near future (2046-2065) and the far future (2080-2100) under scenarios RCP2.6 and RCP8.5.

Figure 6. Extreme sea level in the Balearic Islands. (Top Left) 99th percentile of atmospheric sea level (in cm) for the hindcast period (1986-2005). (Middle) Relative change with respect to the hindcast period under RCP2.6 scenario (Right) Relative change with respect to the hindcast period under RCP8.5 scenario. The projected changes for the near future (2046-2065) are presented in the top row while the projected changes for the far future (2081-2100) are presented in the bottom row

5.3 Wind Waves

Like in the storm surge case, the results are presented in terms of maps including information about the present conditions and relative change (in %) with respect to those conditions. In particular, in the appendix of deliverable 4.3 there are the figures organized by islands, here including only the figures for the Balearic Islands (Figure 7). It includes the 99th percentile of hourly significant wave height from the hindcast simulation for the period 1986-2005 (an average of them when more than one hindcast is available), and the relative change under RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 in two time horizons, 2046-2065 (near future) and 2081-2100 (far future). It is important to highlight that the model outputs have been interpolated to the islands high resolution coastlines for visualization purposes. However, the original spatial resolution is way coarser (1/4°).

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As a summary of the results, Table 3 shows the 99th percentile of significant wave height averaged in each region for the hindcast, and the two scenarios for the two periods. In all the regions a decrease in the extreme wave height is found being larger under scenario RCP8.5. In relative terms the averaged changes are lower than 10% even under the stronger scenario.

Region	Hindcast 1986-2005	RCP2.6 2046-2065	RCP85 2046-2065	RCP2.6 2081-2100	RCP85 2081-2100
<i>Balearic</i>	2,08	2,05	2,00	2,05	1,95
<i>Canary</i>	2,81	2,82	2,79	2,80	2,76
<i>Crete</i>	2,01	1,99	2,00	2,00	2,01
<i>Madeira</i>	3,75	3,74	3,68	3,70	3,57
<i>Sardinia</i>	1,83	1,83	1,80	1,83	1,77
<i>West</i>	2,10	2,09	2,06	2,07	1,99
<i>Azores</i>	4,83	4,82	4,72	4,75	4,55
<i>Baltic</i>	N/D	N/D	N/D	N/D	N/D
<i>Corsica</i>	1,91	1,91	1,89	1,91	1,86
<i>Cyprus</i>	1,43	1,40	1,40	1,40	1,33
<i>Malta</i>	2,27	2,24	2,22	2,26	2,18
<i>Sicily</i>	1,68	1,66	1,62	1,66	1,56

Table 3. 99th percentile of significant wave height (in m) averaged in each region for the hindcast period, the near future (2046-2065) and the far future (2080-2100) under scenarios RCP2.6 and RCP8.5.

Figure 7. Extreme waves in the Balearic Islands. (Top Left) 99th percentile of significant wave height (in m) for the hindcast period (1986-2005). (Middle) Relative change with respect to the hindcast period under RCP2.6 scenario (Right) Relative change with respect to the hindcast period under RCP8.5 scenario. The projected changes for the near future (2046-2065) are presented in the top row while the projected changes for the far future (2081-2100) are presented in the bottom row.

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5.4 Flood level

The 95th percentile of the flood level averaged for the different regions is summarized in Table 1 for scenarios RCP2.6 and RCP8.5 and two time horizons. These values are presented as anomalies with respect to the present mean sea level at beach location (i.e. including the median contribution of runup). In all cases an increase is expected being larger at the end of the century under scenario RCP8.5. The larger values are found for the Atlantic islands, where slightly larger sea level rise is combined with the effect of much larger wind waves. The values in that scenario ranges from 92.5 cm in Corsica and Cyprus to 170 cm in the Azores. Under RCP2.6 scenario the values are less than half, suggesting that a mitigation scenario could largely minimize the negative impact of climate change on beach flooding.

The flood elevation is not spatially uniform in each region, with portions of the coastline more exposed to strong waves reaching much larger values (see Appendix). In any case it is important to remind that those values correspond to high flood events (happening ~18 days per year) in beach locations. In other coastal areas with infrastructures or cliffs, the contribution of the runup is much lower.

Island	RCP2.6 2046-2065	RCP8.5 2046-2065	RCP2.6 2081-2100	RCP8.5 2081-2100
Balearic	43,61	85,68	56,27	119,94
Canary	48,60	104,13	59,92	137,80
Crete	34,79	88,26	47,00	116,54
Madeira	61,34	130,32	71,41	162,91
Sardinia	32,31	70,07	43,23	98,90
West	45,11	87,61	57,35	131,37
Azores	67,55	142,92	77,62	169,88
Corsica	30,09	63,41	40,61	92,48
Cyprus	27,63	64,54	37,50	92,47
Malta	36,25	97,50	49,96	120,18
Sicily	30,93	78,62	42,64	105,36

Table 4. Projected extreme flood level (in the vertical, in cm) at beach locations with respect to the present (1986-2005) mean sea level values averaged for the different islands and two time horizons, the near future (2046-2065) and the far future (2080-2100) under scenarios RCP2.6 and RCP8.5. These results have been computed for a typical grain size of 0.4 mm.

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Figure 8. Projected extreme flood level (in the vertical, in cm) at beach locations with respect to the present (1986-2005) mean sea level values for the Balearic Islands under scenario RCP2.6 (left) and RCP8.5 (right). The projected changes for the near future (2046-2065) are presented in the top row while the projected changes for the far future (2081-2100) are presented in the bottom row

5.5 Loss of beach surface

The translation of sea elevation to beach loss requires a detailed knowledge of the beach topography and shape. At present this is only available for the Balearic Islands, so we focus on that case.

Starting from the transfer matrix explained in Methods and having information of the granulometry and the area of the Balearic beaches, the Runup is directly obtained. With the Runup and the sea level rise projected, we are able to estimate the retreat of the coastline and therefore the decrease of the future beach area, (see equation 1).

$$Flood\ Level = Ru2\% + Mean\ Sea\ level\ rise + storm\ surge \quad (1)$$

Once the Flood Level is calculated, the horizontal flood distance is directly obtained using the slope of the beach. The equation 1 has been used for the scenarios RCP 2.6, RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 and for mean conditions (q50th) and extreme conditions (q99th).

In the next two figures, the flooding of a particular beach (Ses Estanques beach) is showed as an example. Two scenarios are presented RCP 2.6 and RCP 8.5 both in two different time horizons: NF (Near Future, mid-century) and FF (Far Future, at the end of the century) for both mean and extreme conditions (Figure 9 and Figure 10).

We first analyse the case of the mean state, which considers the mean sea level rise, and calm conditions for waves. In our example, the present surface of the beach is 13.605 m² (delimited by blue line in Figure 9). For the near future, the beach surface will be reduced to ~10.000 m² (8.256 m²), under scenario RCP2.6 (RCP8.5), respectively (Figure 9 top row). At the end of the

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century (Figure 9, bottom row), the beach area will be reduced to ~8.900 m² (5.655 m²) under the scenario RCP 2.6 (RCP 8.5), respectively.

Figure 9. Current Beach (blue line) and future Beach (orange area) under mean conditions. Near Future (top panels) and Far Future (bottom panels). Scenario RCP 2.6 (left) and scenario RCP 8.5 (right).

Under storm conditions, not only the mean sea level rise is considered, but the contribution of high waves reaching the coast and the effect of storm surges to estimate the flood level on beaches. To do so, the Runup associated to high waves (q99th) is added along with the sea level rise (mean and storm surge). In this case, under storm conditions, the coastline retreat is much greater than in calm conditions, both in the near future and at the end of the century (Figure 10). It is worth to say that under extreme conditions, the difference among scenarios is practically negligible, because the effect of the runup, which does not depend much on the scenario, is much more important than the mean sea level rise.

Figure 10. Current Beach (blue line) and future Beach (orange area) for extreme conditions. Near Future (top panels) and Far Future (bottom panels). Scenario RCP 2.6 (left panels) and scenario RCP 8.5 (right panels).

We now analyse the whole set of beaches in the Balearic Islands. In this region there are 869 beaches along their coasts and their sensitivity to climate change impacts is very diverse. A first useful diagnostic is the coastline setback (see Figure 11 and Table 5). This is related to the loss of coastal protection that the beaches offer. As an illustrative example, we show the case of the moderate scenario 4.5. Under mean conditions the coastline retreat will be 7m at mid-century and 11m at the end of the century, with significant differences across the region depending on the exposure to strong waves (Figure 11). The retreat under mean conditions is typically larger in the south/southwest area and obviously larger at the end of the century. Under extreme conditions, the retreat increases to 18m at mid-century and 22 m at the end of the century, but in this case the heterogeneity is larger, with some spots where the coastline shows almost a retreat similar to

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the mean conditions and others where it can double that value. Looking at other scenarios (Table 5), for the most optimistic scenario (RCP2.6) we find that the coastal retreat under mean conditions is ~5m at mid-century and ~7m at the end of the century. Under extreme conditions, the retreat increases to ~16m and ~18m, mid and end of the century, respectively. If we see the coastal retreat for the most pessimistic scenario (RCP8.5) under mean conditions, it reaches ~8m (mid-century) and ~14m (at the end of the century). The same scenario under extreme conditions, the coastal retreat increase to ~19m (mid-century) and ~25m (at the end of the century).

	Near Future		
Diagnostics	RCP2.6 (min/mean/max)	RCP4.5 (min/mean/max)	RCP8.5 (min/mean/max)
Coastal Retreat (m) -MC	2.52/4.94/8.32	4.10/6.93/10.65	5.14/8.21/12.12
Coastal Retreat (m) - EC	6.32/16.14/35.25	8.10/18.23/37.55	9.19/19.25/38.12
Beach Loss (%) - MC	1.50/33.86/100	5.56/44.95/100	5.56/51.14/100
Beach Loss (%) - EC	5.56/72.44/100	5.56/77.16/100	5.56/79.18/100
	Far Future		
Diagnostics	RCP2.6 (min/mean/max)	RCP4.5 (min/mean/max)	RCP8.5 (min/mean/max)
Coastal Retreat (m) - MC	4.10/6.93/10.65	7.23/10.93/15.32	9.33/13.49/18.25
Coastal Retreat (m) - EC	8.03/18.19/36.60	11.47/22.31/41.34	13.27/24.33/44.28
Beach Loss (%) - MC	5.56/44.95/100	5.56/62.18/100	5.56/70.32/100
Beach Loss (%) - EC	5.56/77.12/100	5.56/83.97/100	20.39/86.44/100

Table 5. Coastal Retreat and Beach Loss results under Mean Conditions (MC) and Extreme Conditions (EC), in rows, and different greenhouse gases (GHG) emission scenarios in columns.

Figure 11. Mean coastline retreat for the Balearic islands for the scenario RCP 4.5. Mean conditions (top panel), and extreme conditions (bottom panel).

We now check the percentage of beach area loss, and results are summarized in Figure 12a. Under mean conditions (grey bars), we find that, at mid-century, the total beach surface loss range from ~34% under scenario RCP2.6 to ~51% under scenario RCP8.5. At the end of the century the percentage increases to 45% and 70%, respectively. Under extreme conditions (i.e. temporary conditions), the percentages range between 72% and 79% at mid-century, and between 77% and 86% at the end of the century, depending on the scenario. When looking at the area loss in each beach we find large disparity, due to the different shapes of the beaches (i.e. beaches with a long waterfront are more vulnerable). The values can range, at mid-century, from 1.5% (beach and scenario with the minimum value) to 100% (maximum value, totally flooded), under mean conditions. Under extreme conditions values range from ~6% to 100%. At the end of the century, under mean conditions, beach area loss range from 6% (beach and scenario with the minimum value) to 100% (maximum value, totally flooded). Under extreme conditions, values range from ~6% to 100%.

This heterogeneity is clearly seen looking at the maps (see Figure 11 for the RCP4.5 scenario in the near future), with closeby beaches with very different area loss.

If we focus on those beaches that will totally disappear under mean conditions (see Figure 12b), the results range between 9 beaches for RCP2.6 at mid-century to and 107 beaches (for RCP 8.5), at the end of the century. It is important to highlight that here we refer to those beaches that will be permanently lost. Under extreme conditions, which will only last for several days but that

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can be very harmful, the situation tends to be much worse, reaching more than 300 beaches lost under the most pessimistic scenario, (Figure 12b, blue bars).

Figure 12. Percentage of the future lost beach area in the Balearic Islands respect to the current situation (top panel). Number of lost beaches (bottom panel).

Figure 13. Area reduced of beaches (%) respect to the current situation, under RCP 4.5 scenario in the near future. Mean conditions (top) and extreme conditions (bottom).

6 Conclusions

The fate of the beaches in European islands is of paramount importance as it is one of the main assets for touristic activities. Sea level rise and changes in the wave climate would put a risk the beaches as a significant loss of beach area could be expected. Quantitative projections of beach evolution was not available for most European islands, mainly due to the difficulties associated to the required computations. In this work, a new methodology has been developed allowing cost-effective and yet accurate estimate of wave runup for different types of sand beaches. This,

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combined with recent projections of sea level rise and wave climate, has allowed a quantification of the flood level for all European islands as a function of time horizon GHG scenario and beach granulometry. In a second step, this information has been transferred to coast retreat and beach area loss for the Balearic islands, where detailed information on beach granulometry and current area was available.

In order to translate this information to quantitative indicators to be used in the operationalization of the impact chains, a suggestion would be the following. First, we can assume that the distribution of beach types is similar in the different islands. Thus, a rough estimate of the beach surface loss in each island could be derived from the results obtained for the Balearic islands, by scaling the percentage by the mean flood level in each island (Table 4). Then, the area loss can be directly translated to a normalized indicator ranging from 0 to 1. That is, a loss a 50% of beach surface would represent a hazard of 0.5.

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